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OPPORTUNITIES FOR MARBLE POWDER WASTE AS AN ECO-FRIENDLY USE IN ADAPTIVE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS.

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ABSTRACT:

In past few years, Marble is considered as one of the most important decorative building materials. Marble powder is the by product of the marble which severaltly affects the environment and causes many health hazards. Waste is generated from sawing, shaping, and polishing processes. Marble industry produces large amounts of waste as environmental threat.

Construction work requires mostly two types of cement: OPC and PPC ordinary and pozzolana. Scarcity of good quality Natural River sand due to depletion of resources and restriction due to environmental consideration has made concrete manufactures to look for suitable alternative fine aggregate.

Accordingly, natural sand can be substituted with marble powder and used in concretes. Percentage of marble powder used by builders are still negligibile whereas this disturbs the environment in

some part of Southern and Western India are used. In present research real processed marble powder is not available and this makes manufacturing of good quality of concrete very difficult. There is a need for 'clean sand' in the construction from the point of view of durability of structures. Indiscriminate mining and quarrying is posing threat to the environment. As the demand for Natural River sand is surpassing the availability, has resulted in fast depletion of natural sand sources. Marble powder is the answer for this problem especially when some states have already banned the use of river sand for construction.

In this paper the effect of using marble powder as constituents of fines in concrete by partially reducing quantity of natural sand as fines has been studied in terms of the relative workability & compressive as well as flexural strengths. Upon testing it is concluded that Mechanical strength decreases with increasing marble content. Waste marble can be used instead of the conventional aggregate in the concrete paving block production.

Keywords: Marble Powder , Concrete, Compressive Strength, Aggregate, Natural sand.

INTRODUCTION:

Marble is one of the most important materials used in buildings since ancient times, especially for decorative purposes. However its powder obtained from finishing the marble has severe effects on the environment and health. Marble powder is generated from sawing and polishing of marble blocks. About 25% of the processed marble is turn into dust or powder form. About 7,000,000 tons of marble have been produced in the world. 1,80,000 tons Disposal of the marble powder material of the marble industry is one of the environmental problems worldwide today. It affects the environmental ecosystem in which living things are interacted by non living things and being affected. In most of the places of India, the marble powder is kept open or disposed off in open and whenever the acid rain come the marble powder which is CaCO_3 reacts with H_2SO_4 and give this result-

Which is again pollute the environment by emitting carbon dioxide gas so it should be use with the concrete materials by replacement. The natural sand is a very important mineral for the expansion of society. Sand is a naturally occurring granular material composed of finely divided rock and mineral particles. River sand is one of the world's most plentiful resources (perhaps as much as 20% of the Earth's crust is sand) and has the ability to replenish itself. River sand is vital for human well being & for sustenance of rivers. The composition of sand is highly variable, depending on the local rock sources and conditions, but the most common constituent of sand in inland continental settings and non-tropical coastal settings is silica (silicon dioxide, or SiO_2), usually in the form of quartz which because of its chemical inertness and considerable hardness, is the most common mineral resistant to weathering. Some attempts have been made to find and reaching the possibilities of using waste marble powder in mortars and concretes and strength and workability results were compared with conventional cement-sand mortar/concrete. Marble dust can be used either to produce new products or as an admixture so that the natural sources are used more efficiently and the environment is saved from dumpsites of marble waste.

This research paper focuses on using this marble dust with conventional concrete in the mix, which will help in utilizing this non biodegradable substance and will help in controlling environmental as well as various health problems.

Cement:

Cement is the glue that binds the concrete together, and is therefore critical for meeting society's needs of housing and basic infrastructure such as bridges, roads, water treatment facilities, schools and hospitals. Concrete is the second most consumed material after water, with nearly three tonnes used annually for each person on the planet. Being one of the basic elements for setting up strong and healthy infrastructure, Cement plays a crucial role in economic development of any country. Having more than a hundred and fifty years history, it has been used extensively in construction of anything, from a small

building to a mammoth multipurpose projects. In this experiment Ambuja(PPC) cement had used. In general Portland Pozzolana Cement (PPC) has 80 per cent clinker, 15 percent pozzolana and 5 per cent gypsum and accounts for 18 per cent of the total cement consumption. It is manufactured because it uses fly ash/burnt clay/coal waste as the main ingredient.

Marble:

Marble is a rock resulting from metamorphism of sedimentary carbonate rocks, most commonly limestone or dolomite rock. Metamorphism causes variable recrystallization of the original carbonate mineral grains. The resulting marble rock is typically composed of an interlocking mosaic of carbonate crystals. Primary sedimentary textures and structures of the original carbonate rock (protolith) have typically been modified or destroyed. Pure white marble is the result of metamorphism of a very pure (silicate-poor) limestone or dolomite protolith. The characteristic swirls and veins of many colours marble varieties are usually due to various mineral impurities such as clay, silt, sand, iron oxides, or chert which were originally present as grains or layers in the limestone. Green coloration is often due to serpentine resulting from originally high magnesium limestone or dolostone with silica impurities.

Types of marble:

No	S	Name of the marble	Colour
1		Carrara marble	white or blue-gray
2		Murphy marble	White
3		Parian marble	pure-white, fine-grained
4		Pentelic marble	pure-white, fine-grained semitranslucent
5		Ruskeala marble	White
6		BiancoSivec	White
7		Sylacauga marble	White
8		Vermont marble	White
9		Wunsiedel marble	White

Aggregates:

Aggregate is the component of a composite material that provides resistance to the compressive stress. To yield efficiency the filling of aggregate should be much lesser than the finished item, but should vary in sizes. For example, the particles of stone used to make concrete typically include both sand and gravel.

Aggregate size:

Experiments has shown a given volume can be filled with hard spheres if it is first filled with large spheres, then filled with smaller spheres, and then filled with still smaller spheres as many times as possible. For this reason, control of particle size distribution can be quite important in the choice of aggregate; appropriate experiments are necessary to determine the perfect proportions of different-sized particles.

Toughened composite:

Toughness is a compromise between the (often contradictory) requirements of strength and plasticity. In many cases, the aggregate will have one of these properties, and will benefit if the matrix can add what it lacks. Perhaps the most accessible examples of this are composites with an organic matrix and ceramic aggregate, such as asphalt concrete ("tarmac") and filled plastic (i.e., Nylon mixed with powdered glass), although most metal matrix composites also benefit from this effect. In this case, the correct balance of hard and soft components is necessary or the material will become either too weak or too brittle.

Natural Sand:

All along in India, we have been using natural sand. The sand is the natural occurring material composed of finely divided rocks and mineral particle. The volume of concrete manufactured in India has not been much, when compared to some advanced countries. The infrastructure development such as express highway projects, power projects and industrial developments have started now. Availability of natural sand is getting depleted and also becoming costly. Concrete industry now will have to go for crushed sand or what is called manufactured sand and other options like replacement of sand by other ingredients.

With decline availability of natural sand along with the environment pressure to reduce the extraction of natural sand from rivers, the use of manufactured sand by replacement of natural sand is increasing.

Different states implemented the ban on mining of natural sand and with the increasing demand of natural sand for different construction works; many civil engineers have expressed the need to promote use of manufactured sand by replacement in the construction industry. As per report the manufactured sand is widely used in all around the world and different major projects technicians insist on the compulsory use of this sand because of its consistent gradation with zero impurities.

Table No.1 Composition of Mix Design M-25 after Replacement of Sand by Marble

No	S.	Mix design M-25 Per Bag	Replacement of Marble powder				
			OMP*	1	2	3	1
			0%	1	2	3	1
			OMP	OMP	OMP	OMP	OMP
			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
1		Cement(Kg)	50	50	50	50	50
2		Sand(Kg)	124	111.6	109.2	106.8	104.4
3		Aggregate(Kg)	166	166	166	166	166
4		Marble Powder(KG)	0	2.4	4.8	7.2	9.6
5		Water(Ltr.)	23.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
6		W/C Ratio	.47	.47	.47	.47	.47
7		Admixture(ml)	550	50	50	50	50

Design of Experiment:

- The standard cubes of 15x15x15 cm were casted and tested the slump, compressive strength using marble powder at different ratios.
- The natural sand used is passed from the 4.75 mm sieve as per IS 383:1970.
- Coarse aggregate used was crushed dolomite with specific gravity is 2.70 t/m³ and a modulus of fineness is 6.64.
- The cement used is PPC (Portland Pozzolana Cement) content fly ash in it.

Fig.1 Portland Pozzolana Cement

Fig.2 Aggregates

- Now Place these all solid materials one by one in the mixture.
- Start the mixing when the solid material placed in it and sack it properly now pour the water in the mixture and mix the mixture up to 5-7 min.
- Add the admixture in the mix and mix it properly
- Now take the mix in cone for slump test and measure the slump.
- Take the 9 cubes for each mix of 10, 20, 30,100 % replacement for testing of 3, 7 and 28 days respectively.
- Cube is the important part of any construction work so it is filled in three layers.

Fig 3 Concrete mix

Fig 4 Concrete mix

(Cement,Sand,Aggregate and Marble Powder)

Fig 5 Cube casting

Fig 6 Cube finishing

- The material is poured 1/3 by three times and each time it will blow 35-40 times by temping rod
- At last it has to finish and after 24 hours the cube can be pick out from cube mould.
- Now after 3, 7, and 28 Days these cubes were tested in the CTM (cube testing machine) in the laboratory and get the result.

Fig 7 Cube testing machine

Fig 8 Cube testing

Table No.1 Observation of workability by slump test as per IS 456:2000.

S.No	Experimental Report of Workability by slump test		
	Replacement of Marble in %	Degree of Workability	S lump
1	10% replacement	Medium	8
2	20% replacement	Medium	8
3	30% replacement	Medium	7
4	100% replacement	Medium	5

Table 2 Observations of 10MP

Test Conducted 10%	Weight of Cubes	Load in KN/m ²	Load in N/mm ²	Average result N/mm ²
3 Days	8315	436	19.4	19.1
	8200	430	19.1	
	8075	425	18.9	
7 Days	8400	546	24.3	24.1
	8100	550	24.4	
	8325	533	23.7	
28 Days	8225	820	36.4	35.8
	8340	790	35.1	
	8150	810	36	

Table 3 Observation of 20MP

Test Conducted 20%	Weight of Cubes	Load in KN/m ²	Load in N/mm ²	Average result N/mm ²
3 Days	8220	460	20.4	20.2
	8010	458	20.4	
	8330	446	19.8	
7 Days	8300	596	26.5	25.9
	8145	566	25.2	
	8410	588	26.1	
28 Days	8150	790	35.1	35.0
	8175	775	34.4	
	8215	795	35.3	

Table 4 Observation of 30MP

Test conducted 30%	Weight of Cubes	Load in KN/m ²	Load in N/mm ²	Average result N/mm ²
3 Days	8215	400	17.8	17.4
	8110	395	17.6	
	8045	378	16.8	
7 Days	8375	510	22.7	22.6
	8260	522	23.2	
	8360	494	22.0	
28days	8410	735	32.7	32.7
	8200	725	32.2	
	8315	750	33.3	

Table 5 Observation of 30MP

Test conducted 100%	Weight of Cubes	Load in KN/m ²	Load in N/mm ²	Average result N/mm ²
3 Days	8010	350	15.6	15
	7859	340	15.1	
	7935	320	14.2	
7 Days	7950	442	19.6	19.2
	7840	416	18.5	
	7885	438	19.5	
28days	8010	710	31.6	31.8
	7980	705	31.3	
	8030	730	32.4	

RESULT & DISCUSSION:

Calculations

Target mean strength (TMS):-The target mean strength at 28 days is given by

$$TMS = F_{ck} + tS$$

Where F_{ck} = characteristic compressive strength at 28 days.

S is the standard deviation. The value of standard deviation has to be worked out from the trials conducted in the laboratory or field. According to the IS 456:2000, the standard deviation for M-25 is taken as 4 from table no.8 in IS code.

t=A statistical value depending on expected proportion of low results(risk factor).According to IS 456:2000 and IS 1343:1980, the characteristic strength is defined as that value below which not more than 5 percent results are expected to fall, in which case the above equation is reduced to-

$$TMS = F_{ck} + 1.65 * S$$

For M-25 concrete the TMS is -

$$F_{ck} = 25$$

$$S = 4$$

$$TMS = 25 + 1.65 * 4 \text{ N/mm}^2;$$

$$TMS = 31.6 \text{ N/mm}^2;$$

Workability of conventional concrete is carried out by slump test and its standard values are given in the IS (Indian standard) 456:2000. I have performed the experiment of 10,20,30,and 100% replacement of sand by marble powder and get the slump in the medium degree of workability according to the code IS 456:2000 so it is good to get the slump in medium degree of workability.

In the other side the target mean strength value of M-25 is 31.6, calculated by IS code. As I have replaced the sand by marble powder by 10%, 20%, 30%, and 100% there 3 days compressive strength > 40% of the TMS, 7 days compressive strength > 65% of the TMS and the 28 days compressive strength is >98%.so it is better to use the sand we can use the marble dust by replacement as per our convenience and can make the marble powder environment friendly.

Summary:

In construction materials the main objective is to reduce the sand because of the depletion of sand and bans allotted by the state government. Many technicians tried to find out the alternative for the natural sand and giving their views. In this experiment the marble powder is used as an alternative of natural sand by replacement at different percentage. The slump of the mix is of medium degree of workability and that is good for slabs, beams, columns in manufacturing of concrete structures. And as per Indian standard the target mean strength of M-25 is 31.6 and the resulting values are exceeding the TMS. So in this paper mainly focused on the alternative use of sand by marble powder and its results for future scope.

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